

ON RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE

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As a teacher trainer for the subject of History I explained just in my presentation to the teachers of History at this Andijan Institute : In the subject of History pupils and students should be enabled to tell stories of History, but not oriental fairy tales from “1001 Night”.

But today as my farewell to you I would like to tell a story, that sounds like a fairy tale from “1001 Night” ...

The author of the drama is G.E. Lessing (1729-1781), an important German Poet of the “Age of Enlightenment” (18. Century A.C.)

The title of the drama: „Nathan the wise“ (1779) – a story from the time of the crusades in the palace of Sultan Saladin („Salah ad-Din al Aiyubi“) in Jerusalem (12. Century AC).

a) *A Short summary of the story* : Sultan Saladin, who was in debt to the rich Jew Nathan, asks Nathan a trick-question, hoping to get reduction of his debts, if Nathan can't answer the question : Saladin's question was: „Which of the three religions (Judaism, Christianity, Islam) is the right one ?“ And Nathan answers with the famous „Ring Parabola“ :

b) A father had one precious ring and three sons. The ring had the magical ability to render its owner pleasing in the eyes of God and mankind. But because the father loves his three sons equally, he made two duplicates / copies of the ring, which he himself could no longer distinguish from the original. On his deathbed, he called each of his sons separately and gave each one a ring.

After the father's death, the sons get into a fight about which ring is the real one and bring the case before a Court. The judge finds himself unable to make a judgment and advises each of the men to believe in the authenticity of his ring and to live their life in such a way that their ring's powers could prove true.

The future will show, which ring is the real one – but maybe all three rings are only a duplicate / copy, because the real ring was lost !?

c) *Interpretation of the „Ring-Parabola“*: What does this parabola want to say ? The Father symbolizes God, the three sons represent the three monotheistic world religions (Judaism, Christianity, Islam), the statement is : just like the three rings, each of the religions can be the right one ! God loves all people in the same way - regardless of their religious affiliation ! Each religion has its own legitimacy, and all originating in God, one is not higher or more respectable than the other.

d) *The goal of the age of enlightenment in Europe (18.Century A.C.)* was the „Education of mankind to independent thinking and religious tolerance towards other faiths !“

e) I want to say, that my deep personal conviction is : the three world religions are three different paths to the same God - determined by different history and culture ... ! – RAHMAT !